

New gender voting gaps in Spain. Why do women vote for extreme right parties?*

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Abstract

This article uses survey data to explore the hypothesis that gender differences in voting for extreme rightist populist parties are related to the perception of being on the losing side of current mainstream feminism. Here the assumption is that contemporary mainstream feminism focuses on "emancipating" women mainly through their participation within the labour market in a market-liberal-oriented way. The article identifies four profiles of voters who might feel like "feminist losers". First, those are men feeling economically threatened by women's incorporation in the labour market, particularly those in white-collar jobs and liberal careers. Second, men feeling culturally threatened by their perception of the weakening of heteropatriarchy. Third, women who, despite being incorporated into the labour market, do not feel "emancipated" by such

* This is a first draft of a current work in progress. The database used is still under construction.

participation (working in low-paid jobs and enduring double or triple shifts as workers and housewives). And fourth, women who do not participate in the labour market, whose central role is as housewives, mothers and caregivers. We argue that they behave as limited rationality voters in selecting extreme rightist populist parties. Finally, we argue that rightist populist parties act as niche parties in answering the needs, demands and fears of those who feel like feminist losers, while mainstream parties have disregarded them. Our primary analytical strategy focuses on identifying profiles of voters, both in an inductive first and a deductive way second.

Keywords: voting behaviour, feminist losers, radical right populist parties, gender gap, Vox

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Introduction

The European Commission (2018) reported that extreme rightist populist parties have increased electoral support since 1980 in Western European countries, particularly in countries such as Poland or Hungary, increasingly participating in governments¹. These extreme rightist populist parties' rhetoric of opposition to gender and sexuality correlates with "gender backlash"² (Schutzbach, 2019; Dietze and Roth, 2020). Rhetorical opposition to gender and sexual equality is central to nativism in extreme rightist populist parties (Spierings, 2020). Meanwhile, nativism is perhaps the critical feature identified as distinctive for extreme rightist populist parties (Mudde, 2007). Nativism entails maintaining the nation's cultural and racial status quo, privileging the native population over non-natives, and also implying the restriction of immigration. Women are central in the nativist discourses: 1) as the biological and cultural reproductive body of the nation (demographic nationalism) (Gökarıksel et al., 2019); and 2) as an exclusionary mechanism to the extent that they (and sexual minorities) should be protected from aggressive aliens and regressive ideologies (mainly concerning Islam) (Köttig et al., 2017). Their increasing presence of extreme rightist populist parties in parliaments, together with their opposition to gender and sexual equality, is cumbersome because it legitimises patriarchy and hegemonic masculinity ideologies (Tankard and Paluck, 2016). When extreme rightist populist parties enter parliaments, this salient event provides 'summary information' to citizens, sending them the message that social norms no longer punish those holding and expressing anti-feminist or anti-gender equality positions.

In connection with this rhetorical opposition to gender and sexual equality, extreme rightist populist parties are characterised as men's parties. Women are underrepresented among voters of extreme/radical right parties (Spierings and Zaslove, 2015). Despite the salience of this characteristic, the role of gender in voting preferences for extreme rightist populist parties is still quite underresearched (Paternotte and Kuhar, 2018). Even though extreme rightist populist parties have been characterised as male parties, the role of masculinity in the rhetoric of extreme populist parties is under-researched (Sauer 2020). As we develop below, the academic literature focusing on this gender gap is even now affected by androcentrism, failing to recognise the differences between men's and women's electoral support for radical right parties (Coffé, 2018).

It is concerning the gender gap in voting for extreme rightist populist parties, where this article makes its contribution. We will focus on the Spanish case, exploring the plausibility of a new hypothesis explaining the gender gap in voting for Vox. According to the description of several authors, we may consider this party as the representative of

¹Europe and right-wing nationalism: A country-by-country guide. BBC NEWS, <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-europe-36130006>. Access 2021/07/19.

² Phenomenon which has favoured the emergence, in many people, of an aversive, hostile and critical position with respect of the consensus about the egalitarian laws between men and women (Dietze and Roth, 2020; Sauer, 2020).

the extreme rightist populist family in Spain (Ferreira, 2019; Arroyo-Menéndez, 2020; Ortiz, 2022). Furthermore, this is also a male party: in the last Spanish general elections of November 2019, two out of every three voters of Vox were male. Still, one out of three voters was female³.

Furthermore, the connection between nativism and a rhetorical opposition to gender and sexual equality is evident in Vox:

España se está vaciando por falta de nacimientos y la solución no está, como algunos nos quieren vender, en abrir las puertas de nuestras fronteras y decirle al mundo entero: venid a ocupar por sustitución nuestro territorio en ese afán de incorporar inmigración masiva proveniente de otras culturas, que no es fácil integrarla (...) [VOX está en una] lucha decidida por la vida, en defensa de la familia y apostando para que crezca la natalidad en España (...) [porque] de nada valdría ninguna provincia con las mejores carreteras, fibra óptica, escuelas y centros sanitarios si no hay españoles para ocuparla. (Ortega Smith, speech given in Benavente –Zamora, 5 September 2021)⁴.

“(...) y allí hay un centro de MENAS, me encuentro con mujeres que me vienen a contar que los policías les dicen que no salgan con joyas a la calle, con madres preocupadas porque sus hijas llegan por la noche y tienen miedo de ser asaltadas, con trabajadoras de ese centro de MENAS que dicen que las inversiones que hemos hecho allí han sido destruidas por quienes viven en el centro (...) Por cierto, saben ustedes que hablan de las manadas y aquí hemos conocido los nombres, los detalles de una manada de españoles en el año 2016, pero después de esa manada ha habido más de 100 manadas en España y el 70% de quienes están imputados son extranjeros” (Abascal, intervention at public TV debate –RTVE 2019)⁵.

Vox has also tried to push the so-called "backlash" against gender equality and women's and girls' rights. El Diario de Sevilla published on December 6th 2021, that after six months with Vox within the Regional Government of Andalusia, "gender ideology" had burst into the Parliament⁶. In another instance, in the Plenary Session of April 4th 2019, at the Andalusian Regional Congress, Vox proposed that strictly non-medical interventions such as sex change and abortion should be excluded from Public Healthcare services⁷. More recently, in the Regional Government of Castilla and Leon, where a coalition between the rightist Partido Popular and Vox is in office, Vox has tried to reduce the budget aimed at gender equality and has questioned women's reproductive rights⁸.

To summarise, we explore a new specific gender-oriented hypothesis to understand the gender gap in voting for Vox. We label it as the "feminist losers" hypothesis. It holds that both males and females are limited rationality voters and puts oppositional gender discourses at the centre of this research. This new hypothesis is developed after reviewing explanations on gender gap voting for right-wing parties in the next section. After that, our design and empirical strategies are delineated. Finally, the following

³ In the last Spanish national elections of November 2019, 62% of VOX voters were men whilst 38% of them were women (Centro de Investigaciones Sociológicas, 2019).

⁴ El Diario.es, 5 September 2021. Retrieved from https://www.eldiario.es/politica/vox-propone-fomento-natalidad-solucion-despoblacion_1_8274317.html. Accessed 6, December 2021.

⁵ Transcription by DEMOSPAIN SEJ-598 group. Debate can be accessed on: <https://youtu.be/7SKDcB1Io0o>.

⁶ Diario de Sevilla, 6 December 2021: “Seis meses con Vox en Andalucía: la "ideología de género" irrumpe en el Parlamento. Retrieved from: https://www.diariodesevilla.es/andalucia/balance-Vox-seis-meses-Andalucia-ideologia-genero_0_1375962659.html. Accessed: 6. December 2021.

⁷ BOPA nº 51 (1 April 2019) and DSPA nº 13 (4 April de 2019).

⁸ El Diario.es, 8 February 2023. Retrieved from https://www.eldiario.es/castilla-y-leon/politica/pp-vox-vetan-cortes-castilla-leon-propuesta-blindar-derecho-aborto_1_9935304.html

sections present and discuss the findings and conclusions.

Voting For the Right: A Question of Gender?

This section reviews the literature we think is most beneficial to frame our research and explore the relationship between feeling like a feminist loser and voting for the extreme rightist populist party Vox. After looking at the general models of voting behaviour, we focus on how voting for the right has been explained by applying these models. Particularly we emphasise how un-rational voting behaviours are usually attributed to women's electoral decisions and how androcentric bias still impregnates political sociology when explaining the gender gap. Finally, we develop our central working hypothesis for this paper.

Voting Behaviors

We may posit three main explicative models for voting behaviour: a sociological one, a psychological one and an economic one, or a rational choice model (Anduiza and Bosch, 2004). In this article, we shall adhere to a version of the rational choice model known as the limited rationality actors' model to understand gender differences in voting for extreme rightist populist parties. However, some elements of other models will be helpful as well.

The sociological model stresses voters' partisan predisposition anchored in their familiar tradition or social position (i.e. socioeconomic status becomes a predictor of voting decisions). Therefore, electoral demands are vital for understanding voting behaviour: citizens will have particular needs and demands in line with their socioeconomic position, religious adscription or cultural or national identity. Within this context, the concept of "cleavage" is central.

Cleavage is a social division between two opposite sides determined by individuals' position in social structure and, as they profoundly feel it, configures social alignments and political parties (Anduiza and Bosch, 2004: 147). Classical authors pointed out three main cleavages in Western democracies: social class, religious denomination, and national origin. However, and critical to our article, we might recognise androcentrism in those classical works (i.e. a lack of gender perspective) and agree that gender might constitute a cleavage. This is a political issue that generates polarised political opinions (Brooks et al., 2006).

The psychological model, likewise, stresses the importance of social position. But it departs from sociological approaches by focusing on political values' importance in explaining voting behaviours. These values are mental constructs through which citizens process and interpret political information. They explain why people do not always evaluate political information in entirely logical ways: a previously established set of values intervenes in judgements. First, a decision is reached upon the correspondence between the information received and the person's morals, and then a decision is made.

The sociological and psychological models are more deterministic than the economic model of voting behaviour, also known as rational voting. Here, contexts matter more than predispositions (position on the social structure or the values). This third approach derives from Downs and states that the utility that individuals expect from the results of

their actions, including voting for a particular party, generates preferences. In this case, ideology is understood not as a value but as a shortcut, a heuristic resource that simplifies decisions.

In the context of rational voting, electoral supply is relevant. Political supply stands for the political system's (expressly parties') proposals presented to citizens, from which they should be able to estimate the expected utility of their vote (comparing their preferences against parties' electoral offers). While voters will try to maximise their utility by choosing those offers closest to their preferences, political parties will try to maximise their vote sharing by moving along the ideological axis to allow for the minimum distance with potential voters. The model, however, demands too much rationality, time and cognitive capacity from real political actors. Therefore, a more realistic version of this model is the "limited rationality voter" model, in which voters would follow heuristic shortcuts to simplify their electoral decisions (Geys, 2006).

As mentioned before, the limited rationality voter model is the one used in this article. This model allows us to formulate different hypotheses regarding the gender gap in voting for extreme-right populist parties, considering both the demand and supply sides of voting behaviours. While the model has been applied to explain voting behaviour generically, we posit that it should also serve the study of the gender gap in voting for right-wing parties. This topic, however, deserves some further attention since it has been questioned. The gender difference in voting for these political formations manifested itself for the first time a century ago when universal female suffrage was approved. It has emerged again in recent decades, only this time in the opposite direction.

Could it be rational to vote for the Right? Gender gaps and rationality

Since universal suffrage was introduced, until the last quarter of the XX century, women had voted more conservatively than men (Inglehart and Norris, 2000; Klausen, 2001; Ruiz, 2002; Vergé, 2006; Ramírez, 2016). Classical studies of voting behaviour tried to clarify the causes of this female preference for right-wing parties, emphasising precisely their non-rational nature.

Female (mainly working class) conservative voting preferences were attributed to women's lack of education and competence as voters due to their traditionalism and domestic roles. While these explanations, of a sociological and psychological nature, were applied to women, male (mainly working class) preferences for labour parties were explained using an economic model approach (see, among others: Lipset, 1960; Almond and Verba, 1963; Inglehart, 1977). Of course, this does not mean that women were not rational in their voting behaviour, only that the androcentric political science of the 60s and 70s could not imagine that. More recent approaches (Klausen, 2001) have stressed how this early female preference for conservative parties was rational. After World War II, many social democratic parties gained power in Europe, establishing policies that defined men as breadwinners (offering only men full employment policies and salaries high enough to sustain a dependent family). These formations were reluctant, however, to women's participation in the labour market. Most women were housewives relegated to the private sphere, not always supported by their partners in raising their children. Therefore, many of them did not identify with social democracy, and neither did they share the same interest as male workers. As conservative formations defended the role of women within the family better than social democrats, it should be easy to understand

that these parties were the formations that maximised most women's female utility in such a context.

This original gender gap has narrowed in Western democracies since the 80s (s. XX). And so, female voters have become more centre-left oriented than male voters since the beginning of the XXI century (Klausen, 2001; Sauer, 2020). It is now explained from a rational choice approach. It is pointed out that the incorporation of women into the labour market and the rise in cognitive competencies (thanks to increasing education levels) made them develop interests as female workers (demand side). At the same time, left-wing parties incorporated the interest of female workers within their electoral offers (supply side). These adjustments between the supply and demand on gender policies contributed to the upturn of the old gender gap (Togeby, 1995; Ruiz, 2002), although not in a territorially homogeneous way, and having a broader impact on younger generations (Inglehart and Norris, 2000). The reverse of this overturn is a current new male preference for rightist parties. The tendency has even intensified and widened in line with the increasing electoral success of extreme rightist populist parties, whose most significant part of voters are male (Spierings and Zaslove, 2015; Oshri et al., 2022).

This new gender gap has become a prolific research topic in political science, but interesting enough, androcentric approaches are still quite present in the search for explanations. First and foremost, researchers have tried to find single explanations that apply equally to men and women. However, as we just saw before, gender may determine different utility functions for particular voting preferences of men and women. Second, in looking for single explanations, researchers have mainly focused on men's vote as the norm and as the problem that needs to be solved, ignoring why there are women that may or may not vote for extreme rightist populist parties. Consequently, many of these studies cannot explain the electoral behaviour of women towards far-right parties (Coffé, 2018).

We may summarise three main theoretical explanations for the gender gap in voting for extreme rightist populist parties: one focusing on the role of attitudes and preferences; one highlighting the consequences of globalisation in the labour market; and one centring on the interaction of demand-and-supply factors and the bounded rationality of the voter.

Our first explanation points out that women's attitudes and preferences predispose them to vote for less extremist parties. The female electorate may control prejudice better than the male electorate and consequently not feel represented by the extremist and discriminatory discourse of extreme rightist populist parties (Harteveld and Ivarsflaten, 2018). Also, the presence of an anti-feminist agenda and a masculine hierarchical structure in those may hinder the preference of women (Mudde, 2019). Coffé (2019) stresses the correlation between masculine personality characteristics (aggressiveness, sobriety) and the strict, violent, radical discourse that extreme rightist populist parties often use. Finally, higher risk tolerance would make men more likely to vote for these parties even when there is no apparent prospect of electoral success (Givens, 2004). These theories linked to preferences or attitudes have proven to be insufficient to explain the vote for extreme rightist populist parties or to address the gender gap (Spierings and Zaslove, 2015). The question about women's rationality as voters is implicit here: why may some women vote for extreme rightist populist parties that stand against their female attitudes, preferences, values, or rights?

Explanations centred on the labour market are closely intertwined with the consequences of globalisation. As the argument goes, mainly male blue-collar workers had felt their jobs threatened by the arrival of immigrants (Givens, 2004; Norris et al., 2005), and so, many of them had been attracted to the protectionist, nativist and xenophobic discourse of the extreme rightist populist parties (Arzheimer and Carter, 2006; Coffé, 2018). This argument, also known as the theory of the losers of globalisation, has remarkably impacted political sociology. However, its androcentric character is also evident (Ralph-Morrow, 2020). Women participate, and to a large amount, within the service industry and have been affected by globalisation and economic competition. Since the gender gap continues, it suggests that employment (and unemployment) are experiences confronted differently depending on gender (Givens, 2004).

Finally, some authors have focused on the interaction between demand factors linked to the specific needs of male and female voters, on the one hand; and supply side factors, anchored in the characteristic of the electoral competition arena, on the other (Givens, 2004). Spierings and Zaslove, for example, point to the interplay between extreme rightist populist parties and their competitors within the ideological space (Spierings and Zaslove, 2017). These explanations tend to understand citizens as rationally bounded actors.

Developing our hypothesis on how "feminist losers" are rational in voting for extreme rightist parties

We have now presented most of the elements needed to develop our hypotheses. We depart from the spatial theory of voting (the economic or rational choice model) and its assumption about the capacity of parties to move along the ideological axis to become as close as possible to the median voter (to maximise their share of votes). And we argue that mainstream parties have converged in the kind of mainstream gender policies they offer (Ruiz, 2002; Verge, 2006): centred on emancipating women through their economic independence thanks to their participation in the labour market.⁹ We may, furthermore, state that, given how capitalism and liberalism have permeated Western societies, this has been done in a liberal-market-oriented way.

We have mentioned how gender, the place men and women occupy in social structure, affects their utility functions. Therefore, the incorporation of women into the labour market, for sure, has been interpreted and experienced in different ways by male and female citizens. Furthermore, because citizens' position in the social structure results from the intersection between gender, social class, age, ethnicity, etc. (Butler, 1989), there is heterogeneity between males and females in how they have interpreted and experienced women's incorporation into the labour market (and its implications). And thus, some authors point out how extreme rightist populist parties respond to this heterogeneity amid citizens' demands. Among these demands are the "emancipation fatigue", their claim for increasing the status of maternity, for recovering a central social role for the heterosexual family, or their fears regarding the diminishing role of heterosexual masculinity, including the male role as breadwinners when women do also participate into the labour market (Dietze and Roth, 2020, Mulinari and Neergaard,

⁹ All other policies, including those directed to the family, have been oriented by this aim of having women participating into the labor market.

2017). To summarise, extreme rightist populist parties act as niche parties regarding gender issues (Meguid, 2005) directly due to the convergence of mainstream parties upon mainstream gender policies exclusively focused on the liberal-market emancipation of women (see also Cowell-Meyers, 2017). Consequently, we can understand the vote for these parties as a rational election from those profiles of citizens critical to mainstream emancipation policies (who believe themselves to be fraught by feminism), a rational election that maximises their gender utility (see Sauer, 2020). In the following section, we will explore the socio-demographic characteristics of extreme rightist populist parties' voters and define the voter's profile that will have a higher likelihood of voting according to this general hypothesis. Particularly in the case of Vox, most of the existing literature has focused on the affective components and the polarised political atmosphere to explain its electoral success (Oñate et al., 2022). Others have stressed the reaction of Spanish nationalism against the Catalanian secessionist challenge (Ortiz, 2019; Arroyo, 2020). Although anti-feminism in the party's ideology has been widely noted (Ramos-González and Ortiz, 2022; Álvarez-Benavides and Jiménez, 2021), to the best of our knowledge, no article have tried to understand the gender gap in voting for Vox using gender as an explanatory variable.

In the following table (table 1), we try to define the meaning of the "feminist losers" hypothesis for the male and female voters in a two-fold dimension.

Table 1. *Definition of the "feminist loser" hypothesis for male and female voters in a two-fold dimension*

	Economic threat	Cultural threat
Male voters	Incorporation of women into the labour market	Weakening of patriarchy. Change in masculinity roles.
Female voters	Low-payment jobs. Still responsible for the private sphere.	Lack of recognition for maternity and caring roles. Change in masculinity roles.

Source: Authors' operationalisation

As regards the economic dimension, the incorporation of female workers into the labour market can be interpreted as a threat by male voters. Especially when there are quotes for women and in areas with competition between males and females (i.e. white-collar jobs and liberal professions, while in services and blue-collar jobs, gender segregation is still quite present). On the other hand, incorporation into the labour market could be more of a burden than an emancipation exercise for some women. Particularly for those women who can only access low-payment jobs while remaining responsible for their family and household work (being unable to buy services in the free market due to their low-payment jobs within a context of public services scarcity).

Regarding the cultural threat, the increasing role of women as breadwinners may be felt as a threat to the traditional male role within the traditional family model. The diminishing role of men as protectors and providers for women and children might also be experienced as a weakening of patriarchy. This same threat might be shared by some women who felt more secure under a patriarchal system (taking care of their families) instead of going into the labour market to look for a paid job. Furthermore, some women may feel that their role as mothers and caregivers is not socially recognised by current mainstream feminism. The following section will develop our main strategies for testing these dimensions of the feminist losers hypothesis.

Data and analytic strategies

In this article, we opted for a first quantitative exploration of the feminist losers' hypothesis, using available secondary survey data (post-electoral surveys recording voting recall)¹⁰.

One of the limitations of many studies analysing voting preferences for Vox is that this party still receives a limited number of votes in Spain. Therefore, multivariable analyses usually run out of cases applying the "ceteris paribus" logic. This is the case with the main post-electoral databases available for Spanish elections, provided by CIS (Centre for Sociological Research)¹¹. For example, in 2019, Vox received 10,5% of votes, which in CIS study number 3269, amounted to 362 responses. Notably, female answers were only 139, and thus any analysis of the gender gap will lack enough cases for comparison. Our strategy to solve this first problem has been to pool different data from general and regional elections in which Vox have gained some votes since the 2018 Andalusian elections (see table 2).

Table 2. Pooled data from CIS post-electoral studies, number of cases (N, males and females)

Election	Month/ Year	CIS number	N (Vox voters)	Males voters	Females voters
Regional: Andalusian elections	2/2018	3236	123	74	49
General: Spanish elections	1/2019	3269	362	223	139
Regional: Basque elections	7/2020	3293	28	20	8
Regional: Galician elections	7/2020	3294	24	19	5
Regional: Catalan elections	2/2021	3314	123	81	42
Regional: Madrid elections	5/2021	3328	169	107	62
Regional: Castille and Leon elections	2/2022	3352	334	212	122
		TOTAL	1.163	736	427

Source: CIS studies 3236, 3269, 3293, 3294, 3314, 3328 and 3352.

Note: the database upon which the table and its subsequent results rely is still under construction.

In pooling these data, we have kept those socio-demographic and value-related variables common in our surveys and relevant to our hypothesis. First, let's recall the central question in this article: why would voters choose to vote for Vox instead of any other party, and what is the role of gender in doing so? Our argument states that the decision to vote for Vox is a rational one, which voters derive from their utility functions. At the same time, such utility depends on each voter's position within the societal structure and their values, which are affected by their gender (and gender's intersection with social class, age, ethnicity, etc.). Therefore, socio-demographic and value-related variables should correlate in particular ways with voting behaviours (in different ways for men and women). The variables available in our database are presented in table 3 (see appendix for more detailed information).

¹⁰ We are carrying out qualitative interviews at the same time.

¹¹ www.cis.es

Table 3. Variables that can be related to the voter's utility function available in our database

VALUE-RELATED	SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC
Interest in politics Left-right self-placement Ideology (conservative, liberal, feminist, etc.) Religion	Sex Age Civil status Education Income Working status Occupation Size of habitat

Source: Authors' elaboration.

To test our feminist losers' hypothesis, we first explore Vox voters' male and female profiles. We then develop the specific profiles that would correspond to the typology of feminist losers specified in table 1 and run logistic regressions to test if those detailed profiles are more likely to vote for Vox than for any other party.

Gender and voting for populist right-wing parties in Spain

In this section, we explore the role of gender in voting for Vox, the representative of populist right-wing parties in Spain. We have developed several tables summarising the results of contingency tables and mean-comparison analysis for our variables (more detailed results can be found in the appendix).

Table 4 shows that voting for Vox is a rational choice for many voters since the highest percentage of people interested in politics is among its electorate. Regarding values, their utility function seems more related to their conservative ideology (being also the voters located more to the right in the left-right ideological spectrum) than liberalism. However, despite the high number of Catholic voters (expected in a catholic country like Spain), these represent a lower percentage than in other rightist parties.

Table 4. Impact of value-related and socio-demographic variables in voting for Vox vs voting for other parties (male and female voters)

Male and female voters	VOX	Others right-wing	Others (all)
Percentage very interested in politics	Highest percentage	Lowest percentage	
Mean left-right self-placement	Highest (right)		Lowest (left)
Percentage conservatives	Highest percentage		Lowest percentage
Percentage liberals		Highest percentage	Lowest percentage
Percentage Catholic		Highest percentage	Lowest percentage
Percentage women	Lowest percentage	Highest percentage	
Mean age	Youngest voters	Oldest voters	
Percentage married		Highest percentage	Lowest percentage
Mean education			

Mean income	Highest income		Lowest income
Percentage working	Highest percentage	Lowest percentage	
Percentage white-collar workers			
Percentage liberal workers	Lowest percentage	Highest percentage	
Percentage blue-collar workers		Lowest percentage	Highest percentage
Mean size of habitat			

Source: Authors' elaboration based on contingency tables and mean comparison from CIS studies 3236, 3269, 3293, 3294, 3314, 3328 and 3352.

If we explore males and females in their accounts (tables 5, 6 and 7), Vox voters (male and female) remain more interested in politics than voters from other parties. Both male and female Vox voters behave as rational actors, although their rationale and utility functions might differ. We observe that women depart from male trends in being located more to the right of the ideological spectrum and declaring a catholic religion with a higher probability than Vox male voters.

Table 5. *Impact of value-related and socio-demographic variables in voting for Vox vs voting for other parties (male voters)*

MALES	VOX	Other right-wing	Others (all)
Percentage very interested in politics	Highest percentage	Lowest percentage	Highest percentage
Mean left-right self-placement	Highest (right)		Lowest (left)
Percentage conservatives	Highest percentage		Lowest percentage
Percentage liberals		Highest percentage	Lowest percentage
Percentage Catholic	Highest percentage		Lowest percentage
Mean age	Youngest voters	Oldest voters	
Percentage married		Highest percentage	Lowest percentage
Mean education	Lowest education	Highest education	
Mean income	Highest income		Lowest income
Percentage working	Highest percentage	Lowest percentage	
Percentage white-collar workers		Highest percentage	Lowest percentage
Percentage liberal workers	Lowest percentage	Highest percentage	
Percentage blue-collar workers		Lowest percentage	Highest percentage
Mean size of habitat			

Source: Authors' elaboration based on contingency tables and mean comparison from CIS studies 3236, 3269, 3293, 3294, 3314, 3328 and 3352.

Table 6. *Impact of value-related and socio-demographic variables in voting for Vox vs voting for other parties (female voters)*

FEMALES	VOX	Other right-wing	Others (all)
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Percentage very interested in politics	Highest percentage	Lowest percentage	
Mean left-right self-placement	Highest (right)		Lowest (left)
Percentage conservatives	Highest percentage		Lowest percentage
Percentage liberals		Highest percentage	Lowest percentage
Percentage Catholic		Highest percentage	Lowest percentage
Mean age	Youngest voters	Oldest voters	
Percentage married	Highest percentage		Lowest percentage
Mean education	Lowest education		Highest education
Mean income	Highest income	Lowest income	
Percentage working	Highest percentage	Lowest percentage	
Percentage white-collar workers	Highest percentage		Lowest percentage
Percentage liberal workers	Lowest percentage	Highest percentage	
Percentage blue-collar workers	Highest percentage	Lowest percentage	Highest percentage
Mean size of habitat	Largest size	Smallest size	Largest size

Source: Authors' elaboration based on contingency tables and mean comparison from CIS studies 3236, 3269, 3293, 3294, 3314, 3328 and 3352.

Table 7. *Impact of value-related and socio-demographic variables impact on male and female voters of Vox*

VOX VOTERS	Males	Females
Percentage very interested in politics		
Mean left-right self-placement		Highest (right)
Percentage conservatives	Highest percentage	
Percentage liberals	Highest percentage	
Percentage Catholic		Highest percentage
Mean Age		
Percentage Married		Highest percentage
Mean Education	Higher education	
Mean Income	Higher income	
Percentage working	Highest percentage	
Percentage white-collar workers	Highest percentage	
Percentage liberal workers		Highest percentage
Percentage blue-collar workers		
Mean size of habitat		Larger size

Source: Authors' elaboration based on contingency tables and mean comparison from CIS studies 3236,

3269, 3293, 3294, 3314, 3328 and 3352.

Deepening into the role of ideologies, however, two entirely different rationales seem to be present among male and female voters of Vox. As shown in Figure 1, the male vote is more oriented toward conservative, liberal and nationalist values than the female vote. Among female voters, however, we find more people who declare themselves as Christian democrats, feminists, ecologist, progressists, socialists and social democrats. Some may argue that females are less aware and knowledgeable of what these ideologies stand for (and give wrong answers). We say that Vox's female voters have more trouble finding the political solution for their particular gender needs (with a Catholic and right-wing orientation), so they vote for Vox. Although both interpretations remain to be further confirmed with better qualitative and quantitative data, we might not lightly dismiss the idea that women's vote for populist right-wing parties is just as rational as men's vote.

Figure 1. Female Vox voter representation according to self-identification categories.

Source: Authors' elaboration based on CIS studies 3236, 3269, 3293, 3294, 3314, 3328 and 3352.

Let's turn now to the societal position that might affect Vox's voters' utility functions. First, as pointed out at the very beginning and highlighted by almost every article on Vox, this is a male party (see table 4). Of course, being a male in Spain (and any other country) is quite different from being a female. Besides, other socio-demographic variables are crucial. As tables 5 and 6 show, both Vox's male and female voters are younger than other parties' voters, and the youngest has different needs, demands and fears than older people. Furthermore (not shown in tables), the age 18-29 is more populated in Vox than other right-wing parties for males, while the range 39-49 is the most populated for females. Thus, most male voters of Vox are just at the early stage of defining their masculinity and male roles within society, while females are mainly in their care-giving stage (either taking care of children or the elderly). Therefore, males and females will have very different needs, demands and fears related to their gender, so

their utility function for choosing Vox might also differ. Women voting for Vox are more likely to be married (both as compared to male voters of Vox but also to female voters of other parties) and more likely to be working (as compared to female voters of other parties). While male workers are also more likely among Vox's voters, married status is less relevant than for women (see tables 5, 6 and 7). We explore below the occupation status as well, finding some interesting differences.

Educational level is also different for male and female voters of Vox. Both men and women are generally less educated than other right-wing parties (men, see table 5) or all other parties (women, see table 6), but on average male voters' of Vox hold a higher level of education than female voters of Vox (see table 7). Let's, however, look at the percentages of males and females within each level of education (not shown in tables). An interesting picture appears in which female voters of Vox are more likely to be found at different educational extremes: among lower levels of education but also those holding a Diploma o Bachelor's degree. This two-mode distribution pointing toward two different profiles of female voters of Vox is also suggested by the information on income. People with the highest income are more likely to vote for Vox (in general - table 4; also, specifically true for males -table 5) and other right-wing parties (in the case of females -table 6). Nevertheless, the average income is always lower for women in Vox, other right-wing and all other parties. However, looking at specific incomes, we observe that females voting for Vox fall at both extremes of the income axis. They are located among those with the lowest incomes but those with the highest incomes, while male voters are more frequently found in the middle-upper part of the axis (see Figure 2). This different combination of education and income for men and women is also visible when diving deeper into their occupational status. Thus, lower occupational groups are slightly more likely to vote for Vox. But when we compared male and female voters of this party, women holding liberal jobs are more frequently found among Vox's voters than males having liberal careers.

Figure 2. *Male and female voters of Vox in different incomes intervals*

Source: Authors' elaboration based on CIS studies 3236, 3269, 3293, 3294, 3314, 3328 and 3352.

So, to summarise, we find Vox's voters particularly frequently among young males, mostly with secondary education, working with good salaries, many of them non-married. Among the minority of women who decide to vote for Vox, we find primarily mature women (in their care-giving ages) incorporated into the labour market, divided into two groups: one with low education and low income, the other with degree education and high salaries. The above suggests that male and female voters of Vox are located in quite distinctive places within the social structure, including the intersection of their gender with age, education, social class, working situation and occupational status. Furthermore, depending on these positions, they may derive different utility functions from voting for Vox. That male and female voters of Vox behave as rational actors should not be lightly ruled out. Both genres are interested in politics (even more so than voters of other right-wing parties or other parties in general). Male voters of Vox are extreme-right wing oriented, mostly conservative but not more catholic than other right-wing parties' voters. Women are extreme-right wing oriented, with more conservatives and catholic than other parties' voters (including right-wing parties). They are also characterised by their diversity of values (other than conservative, liberal and nationalist), including feminist, ecologist or Christian democratic.

Testing the hypothesis of feminist losers

In table 4, we present the first tentative operationalisation of feminist losers' profiles, trying to capture the two-fold dimension of table 1 (see appendix for further detail on operationalisation). Profiles one and three focus on the economic threat that the incorporation of women into the labour market may represent for males and females, while profiles 2 and 4 focus on cultural conservatism and preferences for the patriarchal organisation of society. We acknowledge that this operationalisation is quite broad and coarse. Unfortunately, however, the CIS studies that contain information on voting recall do not include further details on other gender preferences that will be useful for testing our hypothesis. However, if this line of exploration seems fruitful, we might survey with more adequate variables¹².

Table 8. *Profiling feminist losers in a two-fold dimension*

Economic threat		Cultural threat	
Profile 1	Male	Profile 2	Male
	Working (white-collar/liberal jobs)		+ 60 years
	Income over average		Rural (-10.000)
	Urban (+10.000)		Catholic
	Reproductive age		Conservative
N=721		N=106/128	
Profile 3	Female	Profile 4	Female
	Working		Not in the labour market
	Income below average		Any age
	Reproductive age		Conservative
			Catholic
N=502		Any income (also over average)	
		N=100	

¹² An international survey focusing in the gender gap for right-wing populist parties is planned within the Horizon Europe project UNTWIST (<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101060836>).

Source: Authors' operationalisation based on table 1 and variables available in CIS studies 3236, 3269, 3293, 3294, 3314, 3328 and 3352.

As table 8 shows, once we start building up specific profiles, we face the problem of low N, particularly for profiles 2 and 4. For profile 1, we have 721 cases, most of them voters of PSOE (27%), with 10 per cent voting for Vox. We performed two different operationalisations for profile two, with N of 106 and 128, respectively. Profile 2 votes mostly for PP (65%), with a percentage between 6 and 10 per cent voting for Vox (depending on the operationalisation). Profile 3 has an N of 502 cases, most PSOE voters (28%), with 11 per cent voting for Vox. Finally, profile 4 has an N of 100 cases, most of them voters of PP (65%), with 16 per cent voting for Vox. Given Vox's low percentage of votes in Spain, these low figures translate within each profile. Therefore, we run logistic regressions to compare the likelihood of each profile voting for Vox against any other party. Table 9 presents different models in which ideology is a control variable, and profiles are the independent variable explaining the probability of voting for Vox (1) versus any other party (0).

Table 9. *Logistic regression on the probability of voting for Vox vs voting for any other party (vd) for different feminist losers' profiles (vi). Odds ratios.*

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5
Ideology	1.770***	1.772***	1.771***	1.773***	1.769***
Profile 1	1.645**				
Profile 2(a)		0.263*			
Profile 2(b)			0.469		
Profile 3				1.925***	
Profile 4					0.877
N	16327	16327	16327	16327	16327
pseudo R ²	0.217	0.217	0.217	0.218	0.216

Source: CIS studies 3236, 3269, 3293, 3294, 3314, 3328 and 3352.

As expected, as ideology moves from left to the right, all models' probability of voting for Vox increases. Focusing on profiles, two and three have a statistically significantly higher likelihood of voting for Vox than any other party. These results back up the economic dimension of the feminist losers' hypothesis. However, our cultural dimension (or the operationalisation we were able to run) does not appear to increase the likelihood of voting for Vox. On the contrary, profile 2 is less likely to vote for Vox than any other party.

Conclusions

In this article, we explored the reasons behind the new gender voting gaps in Spain, focusing particularly on understanding why women vote for extreme-right populist parties and how it is rational behaviour. The rationality of women's political behaviours has been questioned in the past due to the androcentric interpretations of a primarily male-dominated political scientist community. However, it still exists in many current explanations of the gender gap in voting for contemporary extreme-rightist populist parties. In the particular case of current female electoral behaviour, it might be puzzling that some women vote for parties with an explicit anti-gender agenda. Most of the literature has focused on explaining why women do not vote for extreme rightist parties (that is, they are less likely than men to vote for those options). But that explanations

make only more puzzling the fact that some women may still vote for extreme rightist parties.

Our approach to answering these puzzling questions is to consider both male and female voters of Vox as rational actors (assuming limited rationality of actors). We have proposed that considering themselves as feminist losers might be one of the reasons behind male and female voting for extreme rightist parties. Voting for Vox will benefit those considering themselves feminist losers either because they expect to revert the situation (strategic vote) or as an expression of disagreement with the current status quo (expressive ballot). So, we suggested males' and females' likely utility functions in voting for Vox, depending on their place within the societal structure. Their societal positions have been derived from their gender, age, civil status, income, working situation and occupational status. Furthermore, we pay attention to their values as another critical factor by which males and females evaluate their societal positions and calculate their utility functions. Overall, we have made explicit that male and female profiles of Vox's voters are pretty different in relevant socio-demographic dimensions that imply diversity in their gender needs, demands and fears.

Many limitations remain, however. First, we have only focused on the demand side, and only in a very rough quantitative way. But our aim is not to demonstrate that the feminist losers' hypothesis is the most relevant explanation for extreme rightist vote. Instead, we just examine its plausibility and potentiality for explaining the gender gap in voting for Vox. Among the more relevant task ahead of us are the testing of this hypothesis by the production of qualitative data, the connection with supply information regarding parties' gender policies, and the recollection of better survey data.

A significant limitation is the fact that we have been arguing about voting for populist right-wing parties but have tested the feminist losers' hypothesis only for the case of Spain. Who might consider themselves a feminist loser might depend on the national context across different countries. Therefore, one step forward that we are also initialising is the generalisation of this analysis to other case studies in Europe.

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Annex 1.

Table A. Results from contingency tables and mean comparison on different variables

Variable	Range	Party	Total			Males			Females		
			Mean	Mode	SD	Mean	Mode	SD	Mean	Mode	SD
Sex	0-Male 1-Female	Vox	36.71	0	0.48						
		Other right-wing	53.92	1	0.53						
		Others (all)	51.66	1	0.5						
Age	18 - 99	Vox	48.16	47	15.78	47.96	47	15.84	48.15	46	15.69
		Other right-wing	54.87	70	17.25	53.91	50	17.17	55.70	70	17.27
		Others (all)	51.94	50	17.27	51.29	54	17.04	52.55	52	17.46
Education	1, less than 5 years to 14, PhD degree	Vox	6.81	4	3	6.93	4	3.05	6.62	4	2.89
		Other right-wing	6.85	4	3.41	7.12	4	3.43	6.61	4	3.37
		Others (all)	6.94	4	3.33	7.04	4	3.03	6.85	4	2.89
Ideology	1, extreme left to 10, extreme right	Vox	7.37	8	1.82	7.28	8	1.8	7.53	8	1.85
		Other right-wing	6.60	5	1.72	6.46	5	1.64	6.73	5	1.78
		Others (all)	4.23	5	2.25	4.17	3	2.16	4.29	5	2.34
Income	1, no incomes to 11, >6.000 euros	Vox	4.59	6	2.17	5.13	6	1.96	3.72	1	2.22
		Other right-wing	4.37	5	2.15	5.26	6	1.8	3.67	1	2.14
		Others (all)	4.16	1	2.07	4.78	6	1.95	3.62	1	2.01
Conservative	0-Non-conservative 1-Conservative	Vox	39.34	0	0.48	41.94	0	0.49	34.8	0	0.47
		Other right-wing	33.15	0	0.47	32.23	0	0.46	34	0	0.47
		Others (all)	10.74	0	0.31	10.2	0	0.3	11.3	0	0.31
Liberal	0-Non-liberal 1-Liberal	Vox	19.34	0	0.39	22.1	0	0.41	14.5	0	0.35
		Other right-wing	23.46	0	0.42	27.8	0	0.44	19.6	0	0.39
		Others (all)	11.05	0	0.31	11.9	0	0.32	10.2	0	0.3
Work situation	0-Not working 1-Working	Vox	61.4	1	0.48	66.6	1	0.47	52.4	1	0.5
		Other right-wing	49.1	0	0.50	56.4	1	0.49	42.8	0	0.49
		Others (all)	52.1	1	0.5	56.8	1	0.49	47.6	0.49	

Occupation (white-collar)	0-Non-White-collar	Vox	27.1	0	0.44	25.3	0	0.43	30.1	0	0.46
		Other right-wing	28.1	0	0.45	27.3	0	0.44	30.2	0	0.45
	1-White-collar	Others (all)	26.1	0	0.43	24.6	0	0.43	27.5	0	0.44
Occupation (liberal workers)	0-Non-liberal workers	Vox	8	0	27.7	7.4	0	0.26	9	0	0.29
		Other right-wing	14.5	0	35.3	13.7	0	0.34	15.3	0	0.36
	1-Liberal workers	Others (all)	11.2	0	0.31	11.3	0	0.31	11.1	0	0.31
Occupation (blue-collars)	0-Non-blue-collars	Vox	59.4	1	0.49	59.6	1	0.49	59	1	0.49
		Other right-wing	54.2	1	0.49	55.6	1	0.49	53	1	0.49
	1-Blue workers	Others (all)	61.6	1	0.48	62.6	1	0.48	60.7	1	0.48
Occupation (militars)	0-Non-militars	Vox	5.1	0	0.22	7.7	0	0.26	1	0	0.01
		Other right-wing	2.4	0	0.15	3.5	0	0.18	1	0	0.01
	1-Militars	Others (all)	1	0	0.1	1	0	0.12	0.7	0	0.08
Habitat	1-Rural: small town: ≤ 10.000 inhabitants	Vox	2.18	3	0.79	21.3	3	0.8	2.28	3	0.75
		Other right-wing	2.22	3	0.79	22.1	3	0.8	2.23	3	0.78
	2-Urban: middle town: 10.001-100.000 inhabitants	Others (all)	2.19	3	0.79	2.17	3	0.8	2.28	3	0.78
Catholic	0-Non-Catholic	Vox	80.2	1	0.39	77	1	0.42	85.6	1	0.35
		Other right-wing	84.4	1	0.36	79	1	0.40	88.4	1	0.32
	1-Catholic	Others (all)	59.9	1	0.49	54	1	0.49	65.4	1	0.47
Marital status	0-Not married	Vox	57.8	1	0.49	55.3	1	0.49	62	1	0.48
		Other right-wing	59.9	1	0.49	62.4	1	0.48	57.8	1	0.49

		Others (all)	18.66	1	1.18	56.1	1	0.49	52.1	1	1
Political interest (very interested)	0-Not very interested 1-Very interested	Vox	18.7	0	0.39	18.63	1	0.39	18.8	0	0.39
		Other right-wing	13.5	0	0.34	14.58	1	0.35	12.6	0	0.32
		Others (all)	15.9	0	0.36	17.9	1		14	0	0.39